

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE OF SALMONELLA SPP AND ANTAGONISTIC ACTIVITY OF PROBIOTIC LACTOBACILLI

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Abstract. In this study, the sensitivity of *Salmonella* strains to a number of antibiotics was studied using the disk diffusion method. Ceftriaxone, cefotaxime and ciprofloxacin showed high efficacy, while the strain was resistant to ampicillin, levofloxacin and erythromycin. The antagonistic activity of *Lactobacillus* (*L. rhamnosus*, *L. plantarum*, *L. fermentum*) strains against *Salmonella* spp was also evaluated. The results indicate the possibility of using these bacterial strains as natural antagonists in the future.

Key words: *Salmonella* spp, *L. rhamnosus*, *L. plantarum*, *L. fermentum*, antimicrobial spectrum.

Introduction.

Salmonella spp. are among the most common foodborne pathogens worldwide and pose a serious threat to human health. *Salmonella*, particularly *S. Typhimurium* and *S. Enteritidis*, are the leading causes of foodborne infections in humans. *Salmonella* infection is usually caused by the consumption of poultry products, eggs, and raw chicken [1]. In recent years, antibiotic resistance has become a global challenge for *Salmonella* control. Many *Salmonella* strains have developed resistance mechanisms to β -lactamases and extended-spectrum cephalosporins. This limits treatment options for humans and leads to high healthcare costs. According to some projections, if antibiotic resistance is not controlled, antimicrobial-resistant pathogens could cause more than 10 million deaths per year worldwide by 2050. Therefore, *Salmonella* has been designated as a “priority pathogen” by the World Health Organization [2].

Traditional strategies such as antibiotic therapy and vaccination have led to the development of multidrug-resistant strains of *Salmonella*. In recent years, the antimicrobial effects of probiotics against various enteropathogens and other health-promoting effects have gained great importance. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of *Lactobacillus plantarum* strain in inhibiting the growth and pathogenicity of *Salmonella enterica* serovar Enteritidis in vitro [3].

Biologically active substances and natural antimicrobial agents derived from microorganisms are important in reducing *Salmonella* infections. *Lactobacilli* (*Lactobacillus* spp.) have been shown to be effective against *Salmonella* and other foodborne pathogens through the production of bacteriocins consisting of organic acids, hydrogen peroxide [4], and proteinaceous substances [5]. In many studies, *L. rhamnosus*, *L. plantarum*, and *L. fermentum* strains have been reported to have high inhibitory effects against *Salmonella* spp. [6,7]. Since the development of natural biopreservatives based on lactobacteria is a promising direction in ensuring food safety, the aim of the study was to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of *Lactobacillus* strains isolated from breast milk against *Salmonella* spp. isolated from food and to determine the antibiotic resistance of the pathogenic strain.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bacterial strains and culture conditions

Lactobacillus strain was isolated from breast milk. Lactobacillus strains were grown in deMan, Rogosa and Sharpe (MRS) (HiMedia Pvt. Ltd., India) broth under aerobic conditions at 37°C for 24 h. *Salmonella spp* was grown for 12 h and subcultured in Mueller-Hinton agar broth (HiMedia Pvt. Ltd., India) at 37°C and used until they reached the early log phase of growth.

Study of the sensitivity of isolates to antibiotics

Sensitivity to antibiotics was studied using the method of Da Cunha L R. et al. [8]. The sensitivity of *Salmonella* isolates to 10 antibiotics, representatives of different groups most commonly used in clinical practice, was studied: chloramphenicol (30 µg), erythromycin (15 µg), cefotaxime (30 µg), ampicillin (10 µg), Azithromycin (30 µg), Levofloxacin (5 µg), tetracycline (30 µg), ciprofloxacin (5 µg), Ofloxacin (2 µg), Ceftriaxone (30 µg) (HiMedia, India). The diameter of the no-growth zone was measured, and the antibiotic response of each culture was assessed as resistant (R), moderately resistant (SR), and susceptible (S) according to the supplier's instructions. The analysis was performed in triplicate.

Antimicrobial spectrum of *L. plantarum* strains

The spectrum of antimicrobial activity against clinical strains *L. rhamnosus*, *L. plantarum* and *L. fermentum* was tested using agar spot analysis. 5 µL of *Lactobacillus* cells grown overnight in 10 mL of MRS broth (HiMedia, India) were applied to MRS agar, and after incubation at 37°C for 48 hours, the cells were killed using chloroform vapors for 30 minutes, and an aliquot of indicator strains ($\sim 10^{6-8}$ CFU/mL incubated in Mueller-Hinton agar broth for 24 hours at 37°C) was placed on a spot with 5 mL of semi-solid agar [8].

STATISTICAL ANALYSES

All experiments were performed in triplicate ($n = 3$) and repeated at least three times independently to ensure reproducibility. The results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

RESULTS

Salmonella bacteria isolated from food were tested for different types of antibiotics and according to the results, Ceftriaxone (3.2 mm), Cefotaxime (2.8 mm) and Ciprofloxacin (2.8 mm) showed the highest efficiency and were included in the sensitive (S) group. Azithromycin (2.2 mm), Chloramphenicol (2.6 mm), Ofloxacin (2.0 mm) and Tetracycline (2.3 mm) were in the moderately sensitive (SR) group. Ampicillin (1.5 mm), Levofloxacin (1.3 mm) and especially Erythromycin (0 mm) were recorded as resistant (R).

The studied *Salmonella* bacteria strain showed high resistance to four antibiotics, including Ampicillin, Levofloxacin, Erythromycin and Azithromycin, which were also within the sensitivity range. This showed that these microorganisms developed resistance to certain drugs, in the next stage, the antimicrobial activity of lactobacillus strains isolated from breast milk was tested against this antibiotic-resistant strain, according to which *Lactobacillus* species showed a high inhibition zone. In particular, a growth inhibition zone of 23 ± 0.3 mm was recorded for *L. rhamnosus*, 27 ± 0.2 mm for *L. plantarum* and 25 ± 0.3 mm for *L. fermentum*. These results confirm their effective antagonistic properties.

CONCLUSION. The high antagonistic activity of these *Lactobacillus* strains against certain food pathogens opens up the possibility of using them as new-generation natural antibiotics or their effective combinations in the future. This result creates an important scientific basis for the development of innovative probiotic-based drugs.

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